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Disclaimer:

This deliverable has been submitted to the European Commission and is currently under review. The final version after the approval may differ.

Deliverable 1.1

Data Management Plan

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4Sir2 Partners

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC1.0	Creative Commons Zero
CC BY	Creative Commons Attribution
CSV	Coma Separated Value files
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital object identifier
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DS	Data Set(s)
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GB	Gigabyte
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ID	Identifier
IT	Information Technology
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier
QA	Quality assurance
QC	Quality control
Q&A	Questions and Answers
PC	Project Coordinator
PDDL	Public Domain Dedication and License
PDF	Portable Document Format
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
RMC	Risk Management & Contingency System
TXT	Text TeXT file
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The current deliverable (D1.1) defines and describes the overall Data Management Plan (DMP) for the 4Sir2 project. The DMP outlines how data will be gathered and handled throughout the lifecycle of the project with specified best practices and scientific standards. To this end, it aims to support the data management lifecycle for all data that will be collected, processed, or generated by the project to maximize its access.

4Sir2 project's DMP will comply with European Commission's (EC) Data Management Plan template ([HORIZON EUROPE Data-Management-Plan-Template.pdf](#) accessed 14.10.2025), as it was refined for Horizon Europe, and will specify how generated data will be easily discovered and accessed, ensuring open access and interoperability. It embodies the condition of the information that is collected, processed, or produced, their corresponding data methodologies and criteria, whether and in what manner these data will be disseminated and rendered accessible and how they will be organized and safeguarded.

This document also describes the accessible data resources and datasets to be disseminated within 4Sir2 initiative. This is the first version of 4Sir2's DMP produced, with a concrete final version becoming available on the last month of the project (M54).

1. Introduction

Data Management Plan (DMP) in Horizon Europe (and previous Horizon 2020) is a document with the objective to describe how the data will be gathered, processed and/or generated, as well as how it will be stored. It is a crucial component of data management focusing on systematically updated instructions of how datasets will be shared by project Partners. This will encourage the project Partners to use DMP as a guide of how to follow FAIR principles as well as the guide of how to manage the project smoothly.

The DMP aims to maximize the value of data in line with the FAIR principles, while ensuring legal and ethical compliance and supporting the broader goals of open science in the line with the overall management of 4Sir2, as also foreseen in the Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA).

Information to produce this deliverable was gathered by the 4Sir2 Consortium through a questionnaire (Annex 1) with several questions regarding data management aspects and in accordance with the FAIR principle. The structure of DMP is also based on European Commission's (EC) Data Management Plan template. The DMP reflects a current overview of the 4Sir2 project based on answers from each partner and should be seen as a living document that will be systematically updated with new issues and information during the project's lifecycle.

1.1. Objective of the Deliverable

4Sir2's DMP, aims to identify and organize all data collected, processed or generated throughout the project's lifecycle, as well as specific standards used, data management policies and potential best practices showcased by the consortium partners.

1.2. Insights from other Tasks and Deliverables

D1.1 is inherently connected with T1.1 – 4Sir2 project Risk Management & Contingency Plan (RMC), which is a reference document for effective and successful management of the 4Sir2 project. The RMP procedural framework relies on the GA and CA and is structured around project management knowledge areas (scope, plans, governance, monitoring, communication, risks, quality assurance) in addition to style guidelines and best practices.

1.3. Connection with other official project's documentation

DMP acts as the operational bridge between legal protection, collaborative patent strategies, and ethical compliance. By aligning the DMP with these three domains, a project ensures:

- legal and commercial security of research outputs,
- clear and fair distribution of benefits among partners,
- protection of human subjects and ethical integrity.

1.3.1. DMP integrated with IPR Management Process

IPR Step 1. Data Identification and Classification

- Partners classify all datasets according to potential IPR relevance (e.g., patentable, confidential, proprietary).
- Classification is recorded in the DMP and updated when new data emerges.

IPR Step 2. Ownership and Rights Allocation

- For each dataset, data ownership and access rights are assigned.
- Assignments are reviewed by the IPR Manager to ensure alignment with consortium agreements.
- Any dataset with unclear ownership is flagged for legal clarification.

IPR Step 3. Secure Handling of Protectable Data

- Datasets marked as IPR-sensitive must follow stricter DMP procedures: restricted access, controlled repositories, and version tracking.
- Partners document how each dataset is stored, shared, and protected.

IPR Step 4. Pre-Publication IPR Review

- Before releasing results internally or externally, a mandatory DMP-IPR review checks: novelty implications, confidentiality status, timing of potential IP filings.
- Approval is required before dissemination actions proceed.

IPR Step 5. Licensing and Data Sharing Oversight

- The DMP defines the licensing model (open or restrictive).
- The IPR Manager reviews all data releases to confirm the selected license does not conflict with commercial exploitation plans.

1.3.2. DMP integrated with Co-patenting Strategy Management Process

1. Co-Patenting Step 1 – Contribution Documentation

- All partners document contributions to datasets through DMP version histories.
- These records serve as evidence for inventorship determinations.

2. Co-Patenting Step 2 – Patentability Trigger Process

- When a partner identifies potentially patentable results, they notify the IPR Committee.
- Relevant datasets and evidence are retrieved directly from the DMP.

3. Co-Patenting Step 3 – Joint Ownership Assessment

- The IPR Committee reviews contributions and determines whether the invention is jointly owned.
- If joint ownership applies, the DMP is updated to reflect revised access and confidentiality levels.

4. Co-Patenting Step 4 – Pre-Filing Embargo Management

- Patentable datasets enter an “embargo mode” in the DMP: restricted access, no public dissemination, controlled internal sharing.
- Embargo duration and rules follow the co-patenting agreement.

5. Co-Patenting Step 5 – Controlled Disclosure and DMP Update

- After the patent application is filed, the DMP is updated to adapt dissemination rules.
- Public release of data is allowed only once this step is completed and validated by the IPR Committee.

1.3.3. DMP integrated with Ethical Board Compliance Process

1. Ethics Step 1 – Ethical Data Identification

- Partners identify any datasets involving personal, sensitive, or ethically regulated data.
- These datasets receive a dedicated ethical classification in the DMP.

2. Ethics Step 2 – Consent and Data Use Alignment

- The DMP documents the consent conditions and ensures data handling complies with them.
- Limitations on reuse, access, or transfer specified by participants or the ethics board are recorded.

3. Ethics Step 3 – Secure Collection, Storage, and Access Control

- All ethically regulated data must follow DMP procedures consistent with ethics approval: anonymization/pseudonymization, encryption and controlled access, separation of identifying information.
- Audit logs are maintained for every access event.

4. Ethics Step 4 – Ethics Compliance Audits and DMP Updates

- The Ethics Manager conducts regular audits to check compliance with IRB/EC conditions, correctness of consent procedures, adherence to storage and access rules.
- Any changes required by the ethics board are immediately reflected in the next DMP update.

5. Ethics Step 5 – Ethical Clearance for Dissemination

- Before any publication or dataset release, an ethics review verifies removal of personal identifiers, compliance with consent limitations, authorization for public dissemination.
- Release proceeds only after both ethics' approval and DMP compliance checks are completed.

1.4. Structure

The rest of the deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 2 provides the methodology of this work and how the FAIR principles will be ruled in the project.
- Section 3 introduces the various data assets in 4Sir2 project and provides a detailed overview of the data assets provided by consortium members.
- Section 4 focuses on the FAIR principles in 4Sir2.
- Section 5 presents internal documents workflow.
- Section 6 focuses on deliverable review process.
- Section 7 present the Quality assurance (QA) and Quality control (QC).
- Section 8 and 9 describes document versioning and sharing policy.
- Section 10 briefly replied to the questions related to the allocation of resources.
- Section 11 and Section 12 cover all the ethical and security aspects.

2. Methodology

2.1. FAIR management of research data

This project implements a comprehensive approach to research data management, following the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), the guidelines of open science, and the latest requirements of research funding organizations. The DMP covers data sharing, licensing, metadata standards, storage, long-term preservation, and security measures, with the goal of ensuring data transparency, reusability, and integrity throughout the research lifecycle.

FAIR Principles – Extended Explanation and Implementation in the Project

The FAIR principles, formulated in 2016, provide a foundational framework for modern data stewardship (<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/> accessed 14.10.2025). Their objective is not only to make data open, but to ensure that data is discoverable, well-documented, machine-readable, and suitable for reuse in future research.

Findable. Data must be easily findable by both humans and machines.

To achieve this:

- All datasets will be assigned to a persistent and globally unique identifier, such as a DOI (Digital Object Identifier).
- Data will be described with rich, standardized metadata (e.g. using the Dublin Core or DataCite schema), including key information such as title, authors, creation date, keywords, data collection methods, and version.
- Metadata will be indexed in open repositories and searchable through academic data portals (e.g. OpenAIRE, Google Dataset Search).

Accessible. Data and metadata should be retrievable using open, standardized protocols.

- Research data will be stored in certified open repositories (e.g. Zenodo, Figshare, Open Science Framework), allowing long-term public access.
- Even when full datasets cannot be openly shared (e.g. due to privacy or ethical concerns), metadata will remain accessible, ensuring that the existence of the data is visible.
- Standard protocols like HTTPS will be used to ensure consistent access.

Interoperable. Data should be usable across different platforms and disciplines.

- All datasets will be published in open, non-proprietary formats (e.g.: .csv, .json, .xml).
- Standard ontologies, vocabularies, and classifications will be used to describe data variables, enabling seamless integration and interpretation.
- Metadata will follow internationally recognized standards to ensure interoperability.

Reusable. Data must be sufficiently described and licensed to support reuse in future research.

- All datasets will include detailed documentation on data collection, processing methods, instruments, and limitations.

- Clear and open licensing will be applied – preferably Creative Commons licenses:
 - **CC BY 4.0** – allows reuse, redistribution, and adaptation with attribution.
 - **CC0 1.0** – it is designed to allow creators to completely waive their copyright and related rights over their work, so that anyone can use it for any purpose – legally and without asking for permission.

Reusability also depends on compliance with ethical and legal standards, such as GDPR.

Implementing FAIR principles will enhance the scientific value, transparency, and longevity of the data, aligning the project with best practices endorsed by the EU and national funding bodies.

Table 1. FAIR guiding principles

FINDABLE	ACCESSIBLE
<p>F1. (Meta)data are assigned to a globally unique and persistent identifier</p> <p>F2. Data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)</p> <p>F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly includes the identifier of the data they describe</p> <p>F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource</p>	<p>A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol</p> <p>A1.1. The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable</p> <p>A1.2. The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary</p> <p>A2. Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available</p>
INTEROPERABLE	REUSABLE
<p>I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.</p> <p>I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles</p> <p>I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data</p>	<p>R1. (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes</p> <p>R1.1. (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license</p> <p>R1.2. (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance</p> <p>R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards</p>

FAIR principles are applied differently depending on the discipline and research method. However, there are at least several elements that should be considered as a common for all FAIR methodologies:

a. Documentation – is essential for ensuring data is understandable, reusable, and shareable both during and after a project. 4Sir2 will use standardized formats, terminology, and structures. All project Partners need to be ensured that files and datasets are named, stored, and documented in a way that makes them easy to locate. Moreover, metadata and contextual information so that others can understand and reuse the data need to be included.

b. Metadata – Definition and Importance

Metadata is structured information that describes the context, content, format, and usage rights of a dataset. Well-prepared metadata allows others to understand, find, and reuse the data effectively. The metadata should be accessible if there are any restrictions, such as IPR or data protection with information whether the data may be accessed as well as how and who should be contacted for access requests. Each dataset will be described using standardized metadata schemas such as:

- Dublin Core
- DataCite Metadata Schema

Metadata will include:

- Title of dataset
- Author(s) and institutional affiliation
- Description of methodology
- Keywords and subject area
- Data format and size
- License information (e.g. CC BY 4.0 or CC 1.0)
- DOI or another persistent identifier

Rich metadata increases the visibility, discoverability, and citation potential of research data.

c. Data formats – the project will use open, non-proprietary, and widely supported file formats to ensure the long-term accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of data:

- Tabular data (e.g., survey responses, experimental results) will be stored in CSV (.csv) format to maintain compatibility with a wide range of tools and ensure machine-readability.
- Metadata and documentation files will be provided in XML (.xml) format. Each dataset will include a README file and a structured data dictionary in .csv format to explain variable names, units, and coding schemes.
- Textual documents such as reports or notes will be saved in PDF/A (.pdf) and plain text (.txt) formats for preservation and accessibility.
- If images are generated or collected, they will be saved in TIFF (.tiff) or PNG (.png) formats to retain full resolution without compression loss.

d. Open Access and Public Data Availability

All research data and related publications will be made available in open access, in accordance with Plan S (<https://www.coalition-s.org/> accessed 14.11.2025). Its goal is to ensure that all publicly funded research outputs are freely and immediately accessible to everyone based on open science policies. Datasets and publications will be deposited in general purpose as well as disciplines specific trusted repositories. Using DOIs ensures that datasets and publications are permanently citable and discoverable.

Table 2. General purpose and discipline specific repositories examples (DOI supported)

Repository	Description	License option	Maximum files size
Figshare	Popular general-purpose repository for datasets, papers, posters, media, and more. Integrates with ORCID and institutions	Creative Commons & custom	20 GB
Open Science Framework (OSF)	Collaborative platform for project management and data sharing. Supports versioning, preprints, and linked registrations	CC0, CC-BY, custom	50 GB
Zenodo	An interdisciplinary repository hosted by CERN and funded by the European Commission. Zenodo supports the publication of datasets, code, and documents, assigns DOIs automatically, supports version control	CC0, CC-BY	50 GB
Harvard Dataverse	Hosted by Harvard, but open to all disciplines. One of the largest research data repositories	CC0, CC-BY	2.5 GB

e. Persistent identifiers – is a long-lasting reference to a digital object such as a dataset, publication, researcher, or institution. All datasets generated by the project will be deposited in a trusted data repository (e.g., Zenodo or institutional repository) and assigned a Digital Object Identifier via DataCite. Researcher identities will be linked using ORCID IDs to ensure proper attribution.

f. Licensing and Rights – Creative Commons – all data generated in the project will be shared with clear licensing terms, using Creative Commons licenses to ensure legal clarity and encourage reuse:

- CC BY 4.0 (Attribution) – allows use, adaptation, and distribution (including commercial use) with proper attribution.
- CC0 1.0 (Public Domain Dedication) – waives all rights to the work, placing it in the public domain with no attribution requirement.
- PDDL (Public Domain Dedication and License) – is a legal tool designed to allow creators to dedicate their data to the public domain. It is allowed to copy and distribute the data with commercial or non-commercial use as well as modify and combine it with other data.

The choice of license will depend on the nature of the data and its intended reuse. Whenever possible, the most open licenses will be used to support the widest reuse.

2.2. Collection of information for 4Sir2 Data Management Plan

The information for this deliverable was gathered by the 4Sir2 Consortium through a questionnaire (Annex 1), which was based on the “Guidelines on FAIR Data Management” with some questions modified. After various modifications the final version of the questionnaire was immediately made available to all 4Sir2 Partners by

RIC. While 4Sir2 Partners corresponded promptly to the questionnaire, this stage was found to be too early to provide all available and detailed information. As this document is a living document, new and updated information will be provided in the next version of DMP as the project progresses.

3. Data Summary

3.1. Purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the project's objectives

The data collected, generated, and reused within this project serve to support the scientific and technical objectives defined in the Grant Agreement. The purpose of the data collection is to enable robust, reproducible, and evidence-based research, aligned with the 4Sir2 project's goals.

The project involves the generation of multiple types of data, including scientific analyses, clinical measurements, imaging data, surveys, simulation models, as well as the reuse of relevant open-access datasets where applicable. These datasets are essential for validating hypotheses, training and testing algorithms, benchmarking methodologies, and supporting cross-disciplinary analysis across project partners.

Data management practices will ensure that all collected or reused data are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR), and handled in full compliance with ethical standards, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), where personal data is involved.

The data activities are integral to delivering the project's outcomes, including novel models, demonstrators, publications, and open science contributions, and will directly contribute to the impact of the project within and beyond the research community.

3.2. Types and formats of the data assets that the project will generate/collect

The following different data types will be collected or generated within the lifecycle of 4Sir2:

- **Administrative data:** This includes deliverables, milestones, recorded meetings, presentations as well as working documents produced within the scope of the project. To better manage and track the documents generated, a repository for the 4Sir2 project has been set up to store documents and information on the project. The repository is based on Microsoft Teams, hosted on RIC space and managed by an administration console. Access is granted only to trusted partners' accounts upon their requests. For increased security, access to the Repository is granted by RIC and is regulated by internal IT procedures. The MS Teams platform for the 4Sir2 project has been organized to store the documents and information of the project based on the structure of the Workplan (WPs folders, meetings, general documents), while the repository can also be used as a collaboration platform.
- **Meeting data:** participants lists, minutes, reports, registration forms, sign-in sheets, attendance logs, presentations, communication logs (emails, chats, forum posts, Q&A logs).

- **Training materials:** include slides, handouts, manuals, tutorials, guides, code notebooks, reading materials, video or audio of live training sessions, webinars, polls, exercises, session recordings.
- **Scientific/Research Output:** As part of our dissemination activities, it is foreseen for 4Sir2 partners to make collectively research publications in the context of the project to disseminate our results in International Conferences and Scientific Journals. Open Access to all the peer-reviewed scientific publications of the project will be provided. Selected publications are foreseen to be made available with the highest standard (Gold Open Access). The rest of the publications will be made available on the project’s website, but also in OpenAIRE’s Zenodo open access repository. More than six (6) open access journal publications and six conferences are targeted, with individual 4Sir2 academic partners and researchers aiming to further contribute, acknowledging the work done within 4Sir2 project, in the fields of chemistry, chemical engineering, biology etc.
- **Dissemination data:** publications (articles, reports, policy briefs, white papers); presentations (slides from conferences, seminars, workshops), outreach materials (brochures, flyers, posters, infographics, newsletters), web and social media content (blog posts, tweets, LinkedIn articles, YouTube videos, web pages), media appearances (interviews, press releases, recorded talks of podcasts), roll-ups.
- **Medical records:** basic patients’ information (age, sex, anthropometric measurements, clinical and behavioral questionnaires), results of lab tests (blood counts, metabolic and liver parameters, hormone levels, molecular and advanced biological data, specific substances levels).

Regarding the overall data format, based on the nature and purpose of the data collected, the data will be stored in a variety of types and formats such as .docx, .csv, .txt, .ppt, .pdf, .mp3, .mp4, .xml, .xlsx, .wav, .zip etc. In some cases, the datasets will not generate any new data. They will reuse datasets in the types and formats which are available within the project.

3.3. Data assets provided by the Consortium members

The data assets introduced in this sub section will be generated and updated during the project’s performance. A more detailed presentation of the data assets produced or collected within 4Sir2 will be available at the next iteration of this document in a form of the template below.

Section	Description
ID	
Title	
Description	
Owner	
Related WP/Task	

License/Privacy	
Data type	
Type of process (stream or static data)	
Data format	
Data store	
Data Security	
Regulatory Constraint Requirements	

3.4. Reuse of existing data

It is recommended to use existing resources for research to enlarge and diversify the underlying database for developments made in this project.

3.5. Origin of data

Most of the data in the project will be generated in-project. The re-used data will come from external and open sources databases as well as from internal databases from the project partners. Databases provided will be assessed beforehand for their suitability by the respective partner. Only technically and legally suitable data from external databases is used in the project.

3.6. Expected size of data

At this stage of the project, the expected size of all data is unknown, as the testing scenarios are not fully defined. The exact size of particular data or datasets will be provided at the moment of data generation and/or submission to open repositories.

3.7. Data utility

The data generated in 4Sir2 will be useful for the project (consortium), for other research projects in a similar field and for companies that want to develop products or systems of a similar nature. Nevertheless, much data generated in this project is subject to intellectual property rights or are part of confidential deliverables and therefore cannot be published. However, data published in public deliverables are made freely available if there is consent of all project partners.

4. FAIR Principles in 4Sir2

4.1. Making data findable, including provision for metadata

4.1.1. Persistent identifiers

All datasets generated in 4Sir2, including those shared internally, will be assigned a persistent identifier. For internal datasets, this may be an internal unique identifier generated by the consortium repository, for datasets deposited in open repositories, a DOI (DataCite) will be assigned by the host platform (e.g., Zenodo). This ensures traceability, version control, and consistent referencing across the project lifecycle, in line with the Grant Agreement requirements on research data management and open science.

4.1.2. Naming conventions

To manage the number of documents created, common rules for file names need to be followed. File names need to comply with the following rule:

1. Deliverables

Deliverable names should follow the terminology and structure defined in the Project Description, ensuring full alignment with the Grant Agreement (GA). They must also respect any formatting or naming conventions stipulated in the Consortium Agreement (CA) to maintain consistency across all project partners.

2. Quarterly Progress Report

- **FILE NAME:** *YYYY_Index_Q_Quarterly Progress Report_vX.ext*

with the following meaning:

YYYY	Year	e.g. 2025, 2026
<i>Index</i>	Number of WP	e.g. WP1
<i>Q</i>	Number of quarters	e.g. Q1, Q2
<i>vX</i>	Version	e.g. v0, v01, v02
<i>ext</i>	File extension	e.g. .doc, .pdf

3. Boards (Steering Committee, Ethical Board) meetings minutes

- **FILE NAME:** *YYX.X. Steering Committee minutes (DD.MM.YYYY)_vX.ext*

with the following meaning:

YY	Meeting abbreviation	e.g. SC, AB
X.X.	Report number	e.g. 1.1, 1.2
<i>DD.MM.YYYY</i>	Data of SC meeting	e.g. 07.11.2025
<i>vX</i>	Version	e.g. v0, v01, v02
<i>ext</i>	File extension	e.g. .doc, .pdf

4.1.3. Metadata

The establishment of metadata for the characterization of the data produced and gathered by the 4Sir2 initiative is essential for promoting open access to the data, particularly in contexts such as data retrieval or access. Several metadata standards exist to comprise various data types, and it may be challenging to identify a single standard that serves all objectives. Consequently, a practical and viable strategy involves reaching a consensus on a shared and minimal catalog metadata schema applicable to datasets disseminated in public catalogs and data repositories, while employing data-type specific schema extensions when warranted.

All metadata describing the research data generated within the project will be shared in a way that enables their automatic indexing within the OpenAIRE infrastructure. The repository in which the data will be deposited provides full compliance with the OpenAIRE aggregation standard, ensuring correct interpretation and integration of metadata with European discovery services and enhancing the visibility of the project's outputs.

To ensure interoperability, the repository supports the OAI-PMH (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting), which enables systematic harvesting of metadata by aggregators, including OpenAIRE. The metadata will be exposed in formats compatible with OpenAIRE requirements, ensuring proper mapping and reuse across national and international platforms.

Once data is generated, the list of metadata will possibly be adapted in further versions of the Data Management Plan.

4.2. Making data accessible

4.2.1. Availability of data

The research data generated in this project will be made openly available whenever possible, following the FAIR principles. Data will be deposited in a trusted, publicly accessible repository that provides persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs) to ensure long-term access and citability.

4.2.2. Accessibility of data

Public deliverables as well as open access publications will be uploaded on the 4Sir2 website (www.4sir2.eu). Publications and public data will be available on open access data repositories such as OpenAIRE (<https://www.openaire.eu/>) and/or Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>).

4.2.3. DataCite Metadata Schema

Implication when using Zenodo:

- It uses the DataCite Metadata Schema as its native standard,
- Currently, DataCite Metadata Schema v4.5,
- Requires compliance with this schema when depositing data and registering a DOI.

The DataCite Metadata Schema includes fields of different priority levels:

- **Mandatory fields** – required for DOI registration (e.g., Creator, Title, Publisher, Publication Year, Resource Type).
- **Recommended fields** – not strictly required but strongly encouraged to improve findability and metadata quality (e.g., Description, Subject, Contributor, Related Identifier).
- **Optional fields** – provide additional detail when relevant (e.g., Geo Location, Funding Reference, Alternate Identifier).

4.2.4. Access management

For open data, no tracking of people accessing the data is planned from the 4Sir2 consortium side. Access to 4Sir2 project MS Platform is provided individually for each user of the project team secured by username (email). The repository applies to a strict policy in granting and revoking access to data and logging the user identity while accessing, downloading, and uploading, including version control. This enables us to restore availability and access to the data in timely manner if an incident were to occur.

4.2.5. Access levels

Access to datasets generated in 4Sir2 follows a three-level model:

1. Open access is provided whenever possible, via a trusted repository, under CC BY or CC0 licences.
2. Restricted access applies when open access would compromise the legitimate interests of the beneficiaries, intellectual property protection or confidentiality obligations; such cases are justified in the DMP.
3. Closed access applies to datasets that cannot be shared due to ethical constraints, data protection requirements (Article 14 GA), or legal obligations. These datasets will not be publicly disseminated and will remain accessible only to authorised project members.

4.2.6. Personal or sensitive data

The 4Sir2 project will generate and process personal data, including special categories of data within the meaning of Article 9 GDPR. These data arise primarily from clinical activities conducted in the project and include basic demographic information (e.g.,

age, sex) and results of laboratory analyses or clinical measurements necessary for evaluating the biological effects of the formulated products. Such data are therefore classified as personal and sensitive research data and require enhanced safeguards.

All personal data will be collected under an approved ethics protocol and based on informed consent, according to national and EU legislation. Identifying data will be processed exclusively by the clinical partners and will not be shared with the consortium. Before any transfer within the project, the data will be pseudonymised by separating direct identifiers and storing them in secured institutional systems. Only coded datasets will be used for research purposes.

Data will be stored in secure institutional environments with controlled access, encryption, audit logging and role-based permissions. Access to sensitive data is strictly limited to authorised personnel directly involved in the clinical and analytical tasks. No personal identifiers will be uploaded to shared project platforms or external repositories.

Any publication, sharing or further dissemination of datasets will require prior verification that the data is fully anonymised and that no re-identification risk persists. Where anonymisation is not feasible, the data will not be made openly available and will be subject to appropriate access restrictions in accordance with the “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” principle.

Given the sensitive nature of the clinical datasets, a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) will be conducted where required by EU and national law, and its conclusions will be incorporated into subsequent DMP updates.

4.2.7. Expiry date for open data

Once approved for publication as open data, the consortium does not envisage an expiry date.

4.2.8. Additional tools

Any data generated in 4Sir2 is expected to be readable with generally available tools (PDF and image viewers, documents readers) or open-source tools available.

4.3. Making data interoperable

It is expected that the level of interoperability will be high as common files and metadata formats will be applied. In case, any other specific metadata will be generated, definitions will be provided in README.txt file. For all published and shared data, English will be used. If languages other than English are used, e.g. for interviews

of local stakeholders, posts in local media, English transcripts/translations will be made available.

The documentation will be written in English, using recognized standard terminology and ontologies. However, the construction of variable and value names will follow general data processing conventions applicable to the research field. A separate list will contain detailed information on value names and their properties. Examples of information to be managed during the project will include, for example, variable units of measurement, variable compilation including the name and label of each variable along with its corresponding values and value labels, frequency distributions for each variable, as well as information on the classifications used and the meaning of the abbreviations used.

Given that not all research datasets collected and generated during the project will be publicly available (e.g. final technology, Partner's know-how), it should be noted that many datasets will remain confidential and therefore not accessible or interoperable.

4.4. Increase data re-use

The ownership of datasets will be assigned to the 4Sir2 Partner who produced and generated data or otherwise agreed by the Consortium in accordance with IPR. Both for internally shared data and for published data, every partner generating data will be responsible for the quality of their data in terms of content (e.g. only data from test run in valid conditions, advanced draft versions of documents, etc.) and formalities, for example, elimination of outliers from numerical data, formatting, internal referencing, correct use of pictures, etc. in project reports. Project Coordinator will check the overall quality of the data and their coherence with the requirements of the latest DMP and will work with the data owner to address any shortcomings.

Open datasets will typically be governed by the Creative Commons licenses CC 1.0 or CC BY, unless more restrictive variant of the Creative Commons license is necessary. Furthermore, Creative Commons licenses will inherently incorporate a disclaimer of liability concerning the reuse of publicly available data.

Clinical data will be processed and shared in accordance with GDPR/HIPAA. Only fully anonymized datasets may be made openly available, potentially under a Creative Commons license (e.g., CC BY or CC0). If full anonymization cannot be guaranteed, data will be shared under controlled access through a Data Use Agreement (DUA), allowing reuse for approved research purposes only. No open licenses (e.g., CC BY, CC0) will be applied to pseudonymized or identifiable data. Non-open Creative Commons licenses such as CC BY-NC or CC BY-ND will not be used as they do not comply with open-science requirements for data.

A summary of data availability is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Data availability

Date	Type	Availability
Underlying data published in scientific journals	Public	Available after publication
Underlying data published in scientific journals	Confidential	Not available for publication because of privacy concerns
Data from public deliverables	Public	Available after approval of EC
Other data	Public	Available after consent of all project partners at the end of the project at latest
Other data	Confidential	Not available for publication

No definite period or time limit is planned for access or re-use of the data. However, the open data will be deposited in a repository that guarantees data integrity on the bit level. At this point no continuous data curation policy to guarantee full long-term digital preservation of datasets is planned. Justification for possible case-specific embargo for published data will be decided by project Consortium. Embargo will be sought primarily in connection with any potential patent application based on project results.

It is expected that most of the data published will be freely available; however, certain project outputs (e.g. technology documentation, final product) might evolve into objects of exploitation after the end of the project and require a one-off sign-up fee and/or a license fee.

For all public open data, it will remain reusable via Zenodo for at least 20 years or otherwise stated by Zenodo Repository documentation.

5. Internal documents workflow and Quality Assurance Process (QA)

Within the project, a unified consortium-wide Quality Assurance process is implemented for all documents, e.g. deliverables and data-related documents. The goal of the process is to ensure consistency, completeness, scientific and technical accuracy, and alignment with the requirements of the European Commission and the project work plan.

5.1. Roles and responsibilities

a. Author/ Deliverable Owner (Lead Beneficiary / Task Leader – Initial level)

- Responsible for preparing the initial draft of the document.
- Ensures that the document is complete, consistent with the task scope, and in line with requirements defined in Annex I.
- Coordinates the collection of input from partners.

b. Initial Verifier (Internal Reviewers – Level 1)

- Appointed by the Task Leader or Work Package Leader.
- Conducts initial verification regarding structure, internal consistency, and compliance with the project template.
- Checks alignment with the DMP, FAIR principles, data governance procedures, 4Sir2 Ethical Guideline in Research, and EC requirements.

c. Advisory Board Members (Independent experts from Advisory Board - Level 2)

- Assess clarity, scientific quality.
- Provide comments and indicate areas requiring improvement.

d. Approvers (Work Package Leader + Project Coordinator – Final level)

- Perform the final approval of the document.
- Ensure compliance with the WP scope, quality standards and 4Sir2 Ethical Guideline in Research.

The Project Coordinator confirms readiness of the document for submission to the EC.

5.2. Review Stages and Document Flow

The process consists of three main steps:

1. Stage 1: Review – Initial Verification

- The Author prepares a draft version (v0.x) and uploads it to the project MS Teams Platform.
- The Level 1 Verifier checks the document for structure, format compliance and scope coverage.
- If the document requires additions or corrections, it is returned to the Author.

2. Stage 2: Revise – Internal Review

- The document is forwarded to at least two reviewers from the 4Sir2 Advisory Board or other consortium partners.
- Reviewers complete the Review Form and insert comments directly in the document.
- The Author revises the document (version v01.x) based on the recommendations.
- If discrepancies arise, the Author and reviewers hold a short working meeting.

3. Stage 3: Approve – Final Approval

- The updated version is sent to the Approvers (WP Leader + Project Coordinator).
- After final approval, the document receives *Approved* status and is assigned the final version v02.x.
- The Project Coordinator prepares a PDF version and submits the document to the EC via the *Funding & Tenders* portal.

5.3. Response Times and Timeframes

Table 4. Standard deadlines for the respective stages

Stage	Responsible	Maximum Response Time
Preparation of draft	Author	According to WP schedule, no later than one month before the deadline resulting from the completion of the work on the deliverable/document.
Initial verification	Level 1 Verifier	5 working days
Internal review	Level 2 Reviewers	7 working days
Final corrections	Author	5 working days
Final approval	Approvers	5 working days

5.4. Versioning and File Management

All project documents follow a unified versioning scheme:

- **v0.x** – draft versions prepared by the Author
- **v01.x** – versions after internal reviews and revisions
- **v02.x** – final version approved for submission to the EC

Each version must include:

- delivery type and date
- lead beneficiary and lead author,
- name of the editor,
- contributors,
- a brief description of changes in the *History of Changes* table.

Project repositories maintain the full version history, with access controlled according to project roles.

5.5. Approval and Submission to the EC

1. After final approval, the Project Coordinator converts the document to PDF/A and assigns the project-specific label.
2. The Coordinator uploads the document to the internal repository as the *Submission Version*.
3. The final deliverable is submitted to the EC through the *Funding & Tenders* portal.
4. The Submission Receipt is archived.

5.6. Data Quality Control (Data QA)

The QA process for data includes:

- verification of data integrity and accuracy before publication,
- assessment of compliance with FAIR principles and the DMP,
- validation of metadata and formats,
- confirmation of compliance with data protection regulations (GDPR).

The Data Owner is responsible for verifying the dataset, while the Project Coordinator confirms completeness and compliance with the DMP. Annex II presents the process flowchart for internal documents workflow.

6. Deliverable Review Procedure (peer-review / internal review)

To ensure the high quality of project results and their compliance with technical, scientific, and formal requirements, all deliverables undergo an internal review process. The procedure covers the appointment of reviewers, evaluation according to defined criteria, preparation of review reports, incorporation of comments, and final approval.

6.1. Appointment of Reviewers

Reviewers are appointed according to the following rules:

- Reviewers are pointed either by the **WP Leader** or according to rule that **Partner X** provides the reviews for **Partner Y**.
- Reviewers may include:
 - subject-matter experts from other tasks or work packages,
 - representatives of project partners not directly involved in drafting the deliverable,
 - external experts (Advisory Board members).
- At least **two reviewers** are appointed, unless the nature of the deliverable justifies a different number.
- Reviewer selection criteria include:
 - thematic expertise aligned with the scope of the deliverable,
 - absence of conflict of interest,
 - availability within the required review timeline.

The list of appointed reviewers is documented and stored in the project repository together with the draft version of the deliverable.

6.2. Review Criteria

Reviewers evaluate the deliverable based on standardized criteria, including:

1. **Compliance with the Description of Action**
 - Does the content match the deliverable description?
 - Have all required elements been addressed?
2. **Scientific and Technical Quality**
 - Methodological, scientific, and technical accuracy
 - Appropriateness of data and analyses
 - Completeness of explanations and justifications
3. **Data Accuracy and Consistency**
 - Terminological consistency
 - Proper use of data sources and metadata
 - Alignment with FAIR principles (where applicable)
4. **Clarity and Document Structure**
 - Logical flow of content

- Language clarity
- Compliance with the project template
- 5. **Ethical, Legal, and Data Protection Aspects (where applicable)**
 - Appropriate anonymization
 - Compliance with GDPR and project policies
 - Proper classification of confidentiality level

Each reviewer submits written comments using the standard Review Form (Annex III).

6.3. Reporting Comments and Approval Workflow

The reporting process follows these steps:

1. **Submission of Comments**
 - Reviewers submit their comments (Review Form + in-document annotations) to the WP Leader and the lead deliverable author.
 - Communication and document exchange take place via the 4Sir2 project MS Teams platform.
2. **Incorporation of Comments**
 - The deliverable authors review all comments and incorporate them into a revised version of the document.
 - If any comment is rejected, the authors must provide written justification to the reviewers and the WP Leader.
3. **Verification of Revisions**
 - Reviewers carry out a brief re-review to confirm that comments have been adequately addressed.
4. **Archiving the Review Path**
 - All document versions, reviewer comments, responses, and annotations are archived in the project's system in folders *Archive*.

6.4. Final Approval of the Deliverable

The roles responsible for final approval are:

- **Project Coordinator (PC)** - for formal compliance and readiness for submission to the European Commission.

Final approval is granted after receiving a recommendation from the WP Leader confirming that the review process has been completed and all reviewer comments have been incorporated or justified.

7. QA/QC procedures for research data (quality assurance / quality control)

The project implements consistent quality assurance (QA) and quality control (QC) procedures for research data, covering all stages: data acquisition, processing, analysis, and preparation of datasets for dissemination. These procedures are harmonized across all project Partners, and their application is mandatory.

7.1. Verification of data accuracy by partners prior to sharing

Each project partner conducts a multi-step data quality check before sharing data with other teams or uploading them to the internal project repository. This includes:

Methodological accuracy check – verifying that datasets were produced in accordance with the established research protocols, measurement standards, and project specifications.

Completeness check – ensuring that all required variables, metadata, and auxiliary files have been generated and properly described.

Cross-review (peer check) – data are verified by at least one researcher who was not directly involved in generating them.

Format compliance check – ensuring that data are shared in formats defined in the DMP (e.g., .csv, .json, .tiff) and compatible with analytical systems and repositories.

7.2. Ensuring data integrity

Data integrity is monitored during transfers as well as long-term storage. The following practices are applied:

Data versioning – the project repository maintains a full version history. Each update is logged, and older versions remain accessible for audit purposes (*Archive* folders).

Access-control restrictions – integrity is protected through user roles and permissions in the repository (only authorized users may modify data).

Automated consistency tests – for tabular data, scripts check for missing records, type inconsistencies, valid value ranges, and inter-table relations.

7.3. Methods for error detection and correction

To ensure high data quality, errors are identified and corrected through:

Input value validation – filtering procedures, validation rules, and controlled vocabularies are used during data creation (e.g., value ranges, predefined categories).

Automated error-checking scripts – identifying:

- outliers,
- duplicates,
- inconsistencies between fields and records,

– missing data.

Manual inspection – applied especially to complex data (e.g., qualitative materials, images, experimental recordings) requiring expert assessment.

Error log – each detected issue is documented along with the correction method and the responsible person.

Data regeneration – in cases of critical errors, partners commit to repeating measurements or computations based on raw data.

7.4. Dataset validation process before repository publication

Before datasets are made publicly available in the target repository (open or institutional), a formal validation procedure is carried out, including:

Final QA/QC audit – an independent team member verifies compliance with protocols, FAIR standards, and the described quality procedures.

Metadata verification – ensuring that the dataset includes a complete description, including:

- purpose and context of data collection,
- variable definitions,
- license and access conditions,
- information on methods and equipment.

Assignment of a persistent identifier (e.g., DOI) – issued only after successful validation.

Reproducibility test – where applicable, an analysis workflow is reproduced to confirm that the dataset supports the published results.

Approval by the work package/activity leader – only validated datasets formally approved by the WP leader may be published.

8. Data and document versioning mechanisms (change tracking policy)

To ensure transparency, reproducibility, and full traceability of changes in research data and documentation, the project adopts a unified versioning and change tracking policy.

8.1. Versioning Policy (Major / Minor Changes)

Version numbers follow a structured MAJOR.MINOR scheme:

- **MAJOR version** (e.g., v01 → v02):

Applied when changes significantly affect the dataset's structure, interpretation, or scientific validity. Examples:

- reprocessing raw data,
- adding or removing key variables,
- methodological updates affecting comparability with previous versions.

- **MINOR version** (e.g., v01.1 → v01.2):

Applied for small, non-breaking modifications such as:

- corrections of detected errors,
- updates to metadata (description refinements),
- formatting fixes,
- addition of non-critical auxiliary materials.

All datasets and documents must include a version number in both the filename and metadata record.

8.2. Archiving of Previous Versions

Previous versions of datasets and documents are preserved to ensure full auditability.

The policy includes:

1. **Repository-managed version history** – all past versions remain accessible in the project repository under read-only status.
2. **Immutable archival copies** – archived versions cannot be altered; modification rights apply only to the newest version.
3. **Automatic timestamping** – each version stores the date of release, author, and a unique internal revision identifier.
4. **Long-term storage** – major versions are archived for the entire duration of the project and the required post-project retention period.
5. All previous versions are stored in *Archive* folders.

8.3. Documentation of Changes in Datasets

All modifications must be transparently documented. The following elements are required:

1. **Change log (changelog file)** – each dataset includes a changelog listing:
 - version number,
 - description of changes,
 - date,
 - responsible contributor.
2. **Commit messages (for repository-based datasets)** – concise descriptions of each change recorded in the version control system.
3. **Metadata updates** – each new version must include updated metadata reflecting changes in methodology, variables, processing pipelines, or quality checks.
4. **Linking to previous versions** – metadata records must provide references to earlier versions (e.g., via persistent identifiers or repository links).

9. Detailed description of the processes for sharing and approving data before publication

The project follows a formal procedure for reviewing data before they are made publicly available. This procedure ensures compliance with legal requirements, intellectual property rights (IPR) policies, Co-patenting strategy, protection of confidential information, and data quality standards. The process consists of three main stages: assessment of publishability, legal and IPR review, and the final workflow for dataset publication.

9.1. Responsibility for Assessing Whether Data Can Be Made Public

The assessment of whether a dataset may be published is carried out by three project roles:

- 1. Data Author/s**
 - responsible for the initial verification of data quality, completeness of metadata, and compliance with FAIR standards.
 - prepares a preliminary recommendation regarding publication (or the need for anonymization/restriction).
- 2. IPR Officer or representative appointed by the institutional partner**
 - verifies rights to the data, input licenses, co-authorship, and any potential limitations related to intellectual property.
- 3. Scientific Work Package Leader (WP Leader)**
 - makes the final decision on publication or on applying access restrictions (open access, conditional access, embargo).
 - consults with other project partners if the data were generated collaboratively.

The decision to publish datasets requires approval from all three roles; lack of approval from any of them triggers re-analysis or data modification.

9.2. Analysis of Legal Aspects, IPR, and Trade Secret Considerations

Each dataset undergoes a legal review that includes:

- 1. Verification of copyrights and licenses**
 - identification of ownership of raw and processed data,
 - examination of whether input data sources (external datasets, software, models) comply with third-party rights,
 - selection of an appropriate publication license (e.g., CC BY 4.0, CC BY-SA, CC0, restricted licenses).
- 2. Assessment of potential trade secret disclosure**
 - verification that the dataset does not disclose partner know-how, strategic results, or sensitive technical/economic information,

- checking whether the dataset reveals operational processes, technical configurations, or technological parameters considered confidential by partners,
- applying data modification, aggregation, strong anonymization, or restricted access if required.

3. Analysis of legal requirements for personal data (if applicable)

- verification of GDPR compliance (e.g., anonymization, pseudonymization, limiting metadata),
- documenting the legal basis for processing and the scope of data being published.

4. Risk assessment for re-identification and disclosure of confidential information

- applying Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) procedures if needed,
- evaluating whether publication may enable indirect disclosure of sensitive values.

9.3. Final Workflow for Publishing Datasets in the Repository

The following workflow is used as the standard process within the project:

1. Dataset preparation by the research team

- data cleaning,
- preparation of documentation (metadata, methodological description, README, data dictionaries),
- initial anonymization or aggregation if necessary.

2. Quality and completeness check by the Data Steward

- verification of dataset structure and metadata standards,
- assessment of FAIR compliance,
- evaluation of the risk of confidential information disclosure.

3. IPR and confidentiality review

- conducted by the IPR Officer / project legal expert,
- preparation of an IPR report: license recommendation, identification of restrictions, risk assessment related to trade secrets.

4. Publication decision

- WP Leader reviews the recommendations and decides on:
 - publication as open data,
 - publication with a temporary embargo,
 - publication with restricted access,
 - withholding publication and requiring dataset modifications.

5. Dataset registration in the repository

- uploading data and metadata to the repository (e.g., Zenodo, Figshare, institutional repository),
- assigning a DOI, choosing a license, completing project and funding information.

6. Final verification and public release

- final approval of the dataset version by the Data Manager,
- public release of the dataset and linking it to related scientific publications, reports, or project deliverables.

7. Archiving and updates

- securing a copy of the dataset in the project archive,
- enabling creation of subsequent dataset versions in case of updates or corrections (versioning).

10. Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to 4Sir2 data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the 4Sir2 principles.

11. Allocation of resources

11.1. The cost for making data

The costs required for making the data collected/generated in the course of 4Sir2 FAIR activities are integrated within the budget of the project. These estimated costs will be needed to cover a set of specific data processing and data management activities, spanning from collection and documentation through storage and preservation over to sharing and re-use.

Regarding the data management responsibilities for administrative documents such as deliverables, presentations, etc., all WP Leaders, Task and Deliverable Leaders are described within 4Sir2's GA.

11.2. Data management responsibilities

Each partner is obliged to respect the policies set out in this DMP. Datasets have to be created, managed and stored appropriately and in line with applicable legislation. The Project Coordinator has a particular responsibility to ensure that data shared through the website are easily available, but also that backups are performed and that proprietary data are secured.

- WP1 leader will ensure dataset integrity and compatibility for its use during the project lifetime by different partners.
- Validation and registration of datasets and metadata is the responsibility of the partner that generates the data in the WP.
- Backing up data for sharing through open access repositories is the responsibility of the partner possessing the data.
- Quality control of these data.

12. Data security

For all data, every partner will be responsible for ensuring the data generated (raw or elaborated from other partner's data) is regularly backed up and stored safely according to internal safety keeping procedures. If such data is also shared internally at the Consortium, the data owner will be responsible also for the methods used to share information. In addition, as some data might be shared with all members of the Consortium through free cloud facilities, e.g. Google Drive.

Data intended for publication will be securely stored in trusted repositories for long-term data retention and maintenance. For this case Zenodo as open access repository has been chosen to fulfill FAIR data principles. Zenodo builds and operates a simple and innovative service that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to share and showcase multidisciplinary research results (data and publications) that are not part of the existing institutional or subject-based repositories of the research communities. Zenodo is also ensuring a system for automatic back up. Depositing the data on Zenodo is free of charge and allows for long-term preservation and curation in compliance with the European Union guidelines. Internal data security regulations will be followed to prevent misuse, unauthorized modifications, and data loss.

The personal data are to be collected as much as possible in an anonymous form, and where that is not possible, they will be anonymized before any sharing. Such files should be kept in a safe location to minimize data breach and research data which is not a part of the medical records will be destroyed after the time that will be stipulated within the informative. Password protection and encrypting might be used to enhance security of data. No personal details shall be shared with other partners of the project.

13. Ethics

4Sir2 project will be carried out in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles. Ethics are considered significant in the 4Sir2 project and are distinct parts of the Grant Agreement (Article 14), while the ethical requirements are the sole purpose of WP5, which sole objective is to ensure ethical compliance with the ethical requirements set in the project.

This reflects to the report of the ethical standards of FAME project which corresponds to T1.1 and D1.2 - Guideline to Ethical Research (M3), which develops the project's social, legal, and ethical activities framework, including the project's methodology for handling social science and gender issues. The framework will ensure the compliance of the project's technologies to applicable laws and regulations (e.g., GDPR), as well as to emerging regulations. It also deals with issues like data sources specification and co-creation, identification of the environmental dimension of the research, and social impact assessment. Moreover, the task will identify ethics and risks associated with the project's technologies, along with guidelines to mitigate them.

14. Other issues

No other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management are currently in use.

15. Conclusions

This DMP has disclosed the plans for data management according to best available information at project month M3, following a structured DMP template. While beneficiaries are encouraged to look for ways to share data with the research community, they are under no obligation to disclose data if this goes against their interests. An update of this DMP will be published at project month M18 as D1.3 First revision of Data Management Plan.

Annex 1

Questionnaire completed by each 4Sir2 consortium partner.

This questionnaire was intended for all partners collecting, processing, or generating data in the scope of 4Sir2 project, with the contribution of each partner included and shaping D.1.1. Data Management Plan. For each data category/data type (these two terms are used as synonymous) you plan to utilize, please provide a separate answer to the following questions, clarifying its underlying attributes.

1. Data summary: the following questions aimed to provide an overview of what types of data will be generated, collected and/or shared within 4Sir2 project.

- What types of data will you collect or generate?
- What will be estimated data volume (MB, GB)?
- What will be the sensitivity level of your data?
- What file formats will you use?
- Will you combine data from multiple sources?
- Are you going to use any data based on your patents?

2. FAIR Data Principle

- Will you assign persistent identifiers?
- Will you create metadata for your datasets? Which standards will you use?
- Where will your data be stored to ensure it is findable?
- Is there any data which will not be published?
- How will access be provided to data?
- Will there be restrictions or embargo periods? For which data? Which licenses will be applied?
- Will you use open file formats?
- What controlled vocabulary and ontologies will be used?
- Will sufficient documentation be provided for data reuse?
- What legal or ethical constraints might limit reuse?
- What license will you use to permit reuse?
- Will any existing data be reused? What is the source of the data? Are there any restrictions on its reuse?

3. Data Storage and Security

- Where will data be stored during the project?
- What data security measures are in your institution?
- How will you manage access to sensitive data?

4. Data Protection and Ethics

- Will personal data be collected?

- Are ethics approvals needed for your work? Do you need to receive approval from institutions' ethics board?

5. Data Sharing and Preservation

- How long will project results be stored? What are your internal regulations for data storage?
- Who is responsible for long-term storage of data?

6. Responsibilities and Resources

- Who is responsible for data management on your team?
- Are there any resources (personal, infrastructure) necessary for your data storage?

7. Additional Notes and Concerns

- Are there any risks related to your data?

8. Additional Comments

- In case of other relevant comments on data management, please provide them here

Annex 2

Annex 3

Grant Agreement number: 101181746

Project acronym: 4Sir2

Project title: A Sustainable, Consumer Centric Ecosystem for
Fruit Bubble Smoothie Production

Deliverable Review Form

Deliverable ID & Title	
WP	
Reviewer	
Date of Review	

Funded by
the European Union

4Sir2 Partners

HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version	Date	Author/Contributor	Changes
01			
02			

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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[2]

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[49]

4Sir2: A Sustainable, Consumer Centric Ecosystem for Fruit Bubble Smoothie Production

1. General Information

Item	Response
Version of deliverable reviewed	xxx
Confidentiality level	<input type="checkbox"/> Excellent <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Sufficient <input type="checkbox"/> Needs improvement
Type of deliverable	<input type="checkbox"/> Report <input type="checkbox"/> Data set <input type="checkbox"/> Demonstrator <input type="checkbox"/> Prototype <input type="checkbox"/> Other

2. Review Criteria

For each criterion, please select a rating and provide comments where needed

2.1. Description of Action Compliant Excellent Good Sufficient Needs improvement

Comments: xxx

2.2. Scientific and Technical Quality Excellent Good Sufficient Needs improvement

Comments: xxx

2.3. Accuracy and Consistency of Data Excellent Good Sufficient Needs improvement

Comments: xxx

2.4. Clarity, Structure, and Readability Excellent Good Sufficient Needs improvement

Comments: xxx

2.5. Ethical/Legal/Data Protection Aspects Excellent Good Sufficient Needs improvement

Comments: xxx

3. Summary of Strength

-
-
-

4. Summary of weakness / issues identified

-
-
-

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101181746 — 4Sir2 — HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-01.

[3]

4Sir2: A Sustainable, Consumer Centric Ecosystem for Fruit Bubble Smoothie Production

5. Recommendations

Recommendation Type	Description	Mandatory
Major changes	-----	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Minor changes	-----	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Editorial corrections	-----	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

6. Overall Assessment

Overall rating:

- Accept as is
- Accept with minor revisions
- Resubmit after major revisions
- Reject

Final comments:

- -----
- -----
- -----

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[4]

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